

1 **TITLE:**

2 Harvesting and Disaggregation: An Overlooked Step in Biofilm Methods Research

3

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21 **SUMMARY:**

22 This paper details the methods that demonstrates three common biofilm harvesting and
23 disaggregation techniques on two surface types, ruggedness testing of a harvesting method
24 and minimum information to consider when choosing and optimizing harvesting and
25 disaggregation techniques to increase reproducibility.

26

27 **ABSTRACT:**

28 Biofilm methods consist of four distinct steps, growing the biofilm in a relevant model, treating
29 the mature biofilm, harvesting the biofilm from the surface and disaggregating the clumps,
30 and analyzing the sample. Of the four steps, harvesting and disaggregation are the least
31 studied but nonetheless critical when considering the potential for test bias. This article
32 demonstrates commonly used harvesting and disaggregation techniques for biofilm grown on
33 three different surfaces. The three biofilm harvesting and disaggregation techniques, gleaned
34 from an extensive literature review, include vortexing and sonication, scraping and
35 homogenization, and scraping, vortexing and sonication. Two surface types are considered:
36 hard non-porous (polycarbonate and borosilicate glass) and porous (silicone). Additionally, we
37 provide recommendations for the minimum information that should be included when
38 reporting the harvesting technique followed and an accompanying method to check for bias.

39

40 **INTRODUCTION:**

41 The definition of biofilm has evolved over the last few decades and encompasses microbial
42 association with a variety of biological and/or non-biological surfaces, inclusion of noncellular
43 components¹ that display differing growth and genetic expression² within a matrix. Biofilm
44 provides protection from environmental stresses such as drying and may render the action of

45 chemical disinfectants less effective resulting in the survival of microbes. The survivors within
46 a biofilm can potentially provide a source of pathogenic microorganisms that are a public
47 health concern³.

48

49 Biofilm methods are comprised of four steps, growth, treatment, sampling (harvesting and
50 disaggregation), and analysis. Growth, the first step, where the user determines the organism
51 growth conditions, temperature, media, etc., is the most considered and reported upon in the
52 biofilm literature^{4,5,6,7}. The treatment step evaluates antimicrobials (e.g., disinfectants) to
53 determine their efficacy either against a mature biofilm^{3,8,9} or the antimicrobial may be
54 incorporated into the surface to determine the ability of the product to prevent or reduce
55 biofilm growth¹⁰. The third step, sampling, includes steps to harvest the biofilm from the
56 surface on which it was growing and to disaggregate the removed clumps^{3,8,11}. The fourth
57 step, analysis, may include viable cell counts, microscopy, fluorescence measurements,
58 molecular outcomes, and/or a matrix component assessment^{8,9}. Assessment of data provides
59 information about the outcome of an experiment. Of the four, sampling is often the most
60 overlooked step because it presumes that the chosen biofilm harvesting and/or disaggregation
61 technique is 100% effective, often without verification¹¹.

62

63 Planktonic suspensions of bacteria, often considered to be homogenous, require simple
64 vortexing prior to analysis. Biofilms, however, are complex communities composed of
65 microorganisms (prokaryotic and/or eukaryotic), exopolysaccharides, proteins, lipids,
66 extracellular DNA and host cells¹². Steps beyond traditional planktonic microbiological culture
67 methods are needed in order to adequately harvest biofilm from a surface and then
68 disaggregate it into a homogenous single cell suspension. An extensive literature review
69 (information not included in this publication) demonstrated that the choice of the removal
70 and disaggregation technique is dependent on a number of factors including species make up
71 of the biofilm, surface that the biofilm is attached to (non-porous or porous), accessibility to
72 growth surfaces (easily removable coupon or physical destruction of apparatus in which the
73 biofilm is growing), surface geometry (area and shape), density of biofilm on growth surfaces,
74 and available laboratory equipment.

75

76 When biofilm is harvested from a surface, the resulting cell suspension is heterogenous. If this
77 nonuniform suspension is to be accurately enumerated, it must be disaggregated into
78 individual cells. Viable plate counts assume that a colony forming unit originates from one
79 bacterium. If aggregates of biofilm are placed on the growth medium, it is impossible to
80 distinguish individual cells which could lead to inaccurate estimates. For example, during
81 disinfectant efficacy testing, if a treatment removes biofilm very effectively from a surface
82 compared to the control, the log reduction could appear artificially large compared to the
83 control. On the other hand, a chemical disinfectant that fixes biofilm onto a surface compared
84 to the control will appear to have a lower log reduction¹¹. This type of scenario could lead to
85 biased interpretation of experimental data.

86

87 In preparation for this publication a review of the literature determined that common
88 approaches to harvesting and disaggregating biofilm include scraping, swabbing, sonication,

89 vortexing or a combination of these. Scraping is defined as physical removal of biofilm from
90 surfaces with a sterile stick, spatula or other tool. Swabbing refers to removal of biofilm from
91 surfaces with a cotton tipped stick or other fixed absorbent material. Sonication refers to
92 disruption of biofilm from surfaces via ultrasonic waves distributed through water. Vortexing
93 refers to the use of a mixer to achieve a liquid vortex of the sample inside a tube.
94 Homogenization uses rotating blades to shear harvested biofilm clumps into a single cell
95 suspension. In this paper, we present three harvesting and disaggregation methods for two
96 different surface types, hard/non-porous and porous.

97

98 A list of recommended minimum information that researchers should include in the methods
99 sections of publications is provided. We hope that inclusion of this information enables other
100 researchers to reproduce their work. There is no perfect harvesting and disaggregation
101 method, therefore, recommendations for how to check the technique are also provided.

102

103 Three common methods to harvest and disaggregate biofilm from common growth surfaces
104 are demonstrated in this article. This information will enable researchers to better understand
105 the overall precision and bias of a biofilm test method. Methods described are as follows: (1)
106 A *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* biofilm grown on polycarbonate coupons (hard non-porous
107 surface) under high fluid shear in the CDC Biofilm Reactor is harvested and disaggregated
108 following a five step combination of vortexing and sonication to achieve biofilm harvest and
109 disaggregation. (2) A *P. aeruginosa* biofilm grown on borosilicate glass coupons (hard non-
110 porous surface) in the drip flow reactor under low fluid shear is harvested and disaggregated
111 using scraping and homogenization. (3) An *Escherichia coli* biofilm grown in silicone tubing
112 (porous surface) is harvested and disaggregated using scraping, followed by sonication and
113 vortexing.

114

115 **PROTOCOL:**

116

117 **1. Vortexing and sonication**

118

119 1.1 Grow a mature *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 15442 biofilm grown according to ASTM Standard
120 E2562².

121

122 1.2 At the end of the 48 h growth period, prepare to treat the biofilm and sample coupons
123 according to ASTM Standard E2871⁸

124

125 1.3 Aseptically insert autoclaved splash guards into sterile 50 mL conical tubes using flame-
126 sterilized forceps. Repeat for all tubes that will receive treatment. Tubes for control coupons
127 do not need a splash guard.

128

129 1.4 Aseptically remove a randomly selected rod from the CDC Biofilm Reactor. Rinse coupons
130 to remove loosely attached cells by gently dipping the rod into 30 mL sterile buffered water.

131

132 1.5 Hold the rod parallel to the bench top, over an empty, sterile 50 mL conical tube and using

133 a flame-sterilized Allen wrench, loosen set screw to drop a biofilm coated coupon into tube.
134 Repeat for the desired number of coupons. Remove splash guards and place in a separate
135 container for sterilization.

136

137 1.6 Using a 5 mL serological pipette, slowly pipette 4 mL of the treatment or control into
138 the tubes so that the liquid flows down the inside of the wall of the tube.

139

140 1.7 Gently tap the bottom of the tube so that any air bubbles under the coupon are
141 displaced. Allow 30 – 60 s between each addition.

142

143 1.8 At the end of the specified contact time, pipette 36 mL of neutralizer into the tubes in
144 the same order that the treatment (or control) was applied.

145

146 NOTE: The final volume of combined treatment and neutralizer is important for accurately
147 determining biofilm log density.

148

149 1.9 Vortex each tube on the highest setting for 30 ± 5 s. Ensure that a complete vortex is
150 achieved.

151

152 NOTE: Caution should be exercised when vortexing heavy coupons such as stainless steel in
153 glass vials where breakage could occur.

154

155 1.10 Determine optimal number of tubes per bath and placement within the test tube rack
156 prior to processing actual samples. If processing multiple samples, confirm that the water
157 temperature in the sonicating bath is 21 ± 2 °C.

158

159 1.11 Place tubes in tube rack suspended in degassed sonicator such that water level in bath
160 is equal to liquid level in tubes. Sonicate at 45 kHz, 100% power and Normal function for $30 \pm$
161 5 s. Repeat vortex and sonication cycles and then end with a final vortex (5 cycles total).

162

163 NOTE: These tubes with the harvested and disaggregated biofilm are the 10^0 dilution.

164

165 1.12 Serially dilute sample in buffered water. Plate on R2A agar using appropriate plating
166 method. Incubate at 36 ± 2 °C for 24 h. Count colonies as appropriate to plating method used
167 and record data.

168

169 **2. Scraping and homogenization**

170

171 2.1 Grow a mature *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 15442 biofilm according to the ASTM Standard
172 E2647¹³.

173

174 2.2 Set up the sampling station to include sampling board, 95% ethanol in a beaker, alcohol
175 burner, hemostats, coupon removal tool, beakers with sterile dilution water and dilution tubes
176 for rinsing the coupons.

177

178 2.3 Turn off the pump. Remove a channel cover and use sterile coupon removal tool and
179 hemostats to remove the coupon, being careful not to disturb the biofilm.

180

181 2.4 Rinse the coupon by gently immersing, with a fluid motion, in 45 mL of sterile dilution
182 water (contained in a 50 mL centrifuge tube). Immediately reverse the motion to remove the
183 coupon.

184

185 2.5 Place the coupon into a beaker containing 45 mL of sterile dilution water. Scrape the
186 biofilm-covered coupon surface in a downward direction for approximately 15 s, using a sterile
187 spatula or scraper. Rinse the spatula or scraper by stirring it in the beaker. Repeat the scraping
188 and rinsing process 3-4 times, ensuring full coverage of the coupon surface.

189

190 2.6 Rinse the coupon by holding it at a 60° angle over the sterile beaker and pipetting 1 mL
191 of sterile dilution water over the surface of the coupon. Repeat for a total of 5 rinses. The
192 final volume in the beaker is 50 mL.

193

194 NOTE: The final volume of combined treatment and neutralizer is important for accurately
195 determining biofilm log density.

196

197 2.7 Replace each channel cover as the coupons are removed.

198

199 2.8 Working in the biosafety cabinet, homogenize the scraped biofilm sample. Attach a
200 sterile homogenizer probe to the homogenizer, place the probe tip in the liquid, turn the
201 homogenizer on and ramp up to 20,500 rpm.

202

203 2.9 Homogenize the sample for 30 s. Turn down the RPMs and switch the homogenizer
204 off.

205

206 2.10 Sanitize the probe between biofilm samples by homogenizing a 9 mL of sterile dilution
207 blank at 20,500 rpm for 30 s as described above. Homogenize a 9 mL tube of 70% ethanol for
208 30 s, detach the probe and let stand in the ethanol tube for 1 min. Homogenize two additional
209 dilution blanks.

210

211 NOTE: A disposable homogenizer probe may be used for each sample.

212

213 2.11 Serially dilute the samples in buffered water. Plate on R2A agar using the appropriate
214 plating method. Incubate plates at $36 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, count colonies as appropriate to plating
215 method used and record data.

216

217 3. Scraping, vortexing and sonication

218

219 3.1 Grow a mature *Escherichia coli* ATCC 53498 biofilm in silicone catheter tubing¹⁰.

220

221 3.2 Prepare sampling materials: rinse tubes, sterile centrifuge tube, empty sterile Petri
222 dish, flame sterilized stainless steel hemostat and scissors, timer, and ruler.

223

224 3.3 With pump paused, use 70% ethanol to clean the outside of the tubing. Measure 2 cm
225 from the end, avoiding the area attached to the connector, and mark the tubing to determine
226 cutting locations.

227

228 3.4 With flame sterilized scissors, cut the tubing on the 2 cm mark and place segment in
229 empty sterile Petri dish. Wipe the tubing with 70% ethanol and reconnect the distal end to
230 waste tubing.

231

232 3.5 Rinse tubing segment to remove planktonic cells. With flame sterilized forceps, gently
233 immerse tubing segment into 20 mL of sterile dilution water then immediately remove. Place
234 the segment into 10 mL of neutralizer.

235

236 3.6 With flame sterilized forceps, hold the tubing segment and scrape with sterile wooden
237 applicator stick until all inner areas of the tubing have been scraped. Occasionally rinse the
238 stick in the 10 mL of neutralizer and place the segment back into the sample tube. The scraped
239 tubing segment is the 10^0 or 0 dilution.

240

241 NOTE: The final volume of combined treatment and neutralizer is important for accurately
242 determining biofilm log density.

243

244 3.7 Vortex each tube on the highest setting for 30 ± 5 s. Place the tube in tube rack
245 suspended in sonicator such that water level in bath is equal to liquid level in tubes. Sonicate
246 at 45 kHz, 100% power and Normal function for 30 ± 5 seconds. Repeat vortex and sonication
247 cycles then end with a final vortex.

248

249 NOTE: This tube with the harvested and disaggregated biofilm is the 10^0 dilution.

250

251 3.8 Serially dilute the samples in buffered water. Plate on Tryptic Soy Agar using the
252 appropriate plating method.

253

254 3.9 Incubate plates at 36 ± 2 °C for 24 h. Count colonies as appropriate to plating method
255 used, record data and calculate the arithmetic mean.

256

257 REPRESENTATIVE RESULTS:

258 Validation/Confirmation of a Harvesting Method

259 Several studies that were conducted in our laboratory examined the ability of vortexing and
260 sonication to effectively harvest biofilm grown in the biofilm reactor (ASTM E2562)² using the
261 Single Tube Method (ASTM E2871)⁸.

262

263 *A. P. aeruginosa* ATCC 15442 biofilm was grown according to ASTM E2562² on borosilicate glass
264 coupons. After 48 hours, four coupons were placed into vials, “treated” with 4 mL sterile

265 buffered water and neutralized with 36 mL of 2x D/E Neutralizing Broth. The initial sonication
266 setting of 45 kHz, 10% power, Sweep setting, 30 +/- 5 s was used to harvest and disaggregate
267 the biofilm from three of the four coupons. Upon completion of the vortex and sonication
268 cycle, each coupon was stained with crystal violet and photographed. **Figure 1** demonstrates
269 the amount of biofilm remaining on the three coupons after vortexing and sonication as
270 compared to the control.

271
272 To test this further, a *P. aeruginosa* ATCC 15442 biofilm was grown as described previously
273 and two sonication settings were compared: 1) 45 kHz, 10% power, Sweep setting, 30 +/- 5
274 seconds and 2) 45 kHz, 100% power, Normal setting, 30 +/- 5 seconds. One coupon from each
275 set of the three was stained with BacLight Live/Dead stain and imaged using confocal
276 microscopy (CM). The remaining two coupons from each set were diluted, plated and
277 enumerated for viable cells. The viable plate count results were 9.230 Log₁₀ CFU/coupon +/-
278 0.007 (SD_R) for setting 1 and 9.272 Log₁₀ CFU/coupon +/- 0.066 (SD_R) for sonication setting
279 2. This data corroborated a 2015 EPA Single Tube Method Collaborative Study where 9.03
280 Log₁₀ CFU/coupon +/- 0.272 (SD_R) was achieved⁹. According to the viable plate counts, it
281 appears that all three means are similar enough to not warrant further investigation into
282 differences between the two harvesting methods. However, the microscopic images shown
283 in **Figure 2** may suggest that more biofilm remained after use of setting 1 than setting 2. While
284 we observe that biofilm remaining on the coupons appears dead (red in color), interpretation
285 of viability when using BacLight Live/Dead stain is difficult^{14, 15}. Rather than focusing on
286 viability implications of the stained biofilm, we used this stain to visualize biofilm remaining
287 on the surfaces. Additionally, while we acknowledge that sonication could be deleterious to
288 bacterial viability, a 2007 publication by Kobayashi et al.¹⁶ demonstrated that increased
289 sonication time beyond 5 minutes resulted in decreased viable plate counts. Since our study
290 used a total of 1 minute sonication, we are confident that few cells were killed via sonication
291 as shown by the >9.2 LOG₁₀ CFU/coupons for the two sonication parameters. It is interesting
292 that a complete harvest of the biofilm from the surface was not achieved by either method.
293 This finding demonstrates that viable plate counts alone are not adequate to determine
294 harvesting and disaggregation bias and therefore must be paired with an additional method,
295 microscopy, for example.

296
297 In addition to the sonicator settings, we investigated other important factors that affect
298 sonication. These included the volume of liquid in the vials (10 or 40 mL), the type of liquid in
299 the vial (buffered water or 2X D/E Neutralizing Broth) and the number of vials placed in the
300 bath at the same time (3 or 12 vials)⁹.

301
302 *P. aeruginosa* biofilms on CDC Biofilm Reactor coupons were sonicated using sonicator setting
303 2 (45 kHz, 100% power, Normal setting, 30 +/- 5 seconds). All samples were vortexed either 3
304 at a time or 6 at a time using a vortexer fitted with a 6-place tube attachment then sonicated
305 as described in **Figure 3**. One coupon from each of the following categories was imaged using
306 CM (**Figure 3**).

307
308 In the second study where sonication parameters were investigated, the microscopic images

309 (Figure 3) suggest that minimizing the volume in the tubes, reducing the number of tubes
310 processed at once and use of D/E Neutralizing Broth (which contains surfactant) all contribute
311 to enhanced biofilm harvesting from the coupons.
312

313 Biocides may positively or negatively enhance harvesting and disaggregation. Similar to
314 confirming that a neutralizer effectively stops the active while not increasing kill prior to
315 performing an efficacy test, it is important to confirm that a biocide does not differentially
316 impact harvesting and disaggregation. For efficacy testing, bias results if and only if there is
317 differential removal for the control vs treated biofilm samples¹¹.

318

319 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

320

321 **Figure 1: Photos of coupons stained with crystal violet demonstrating residual biofilm.** A)
322 Coupon removed from the reactor and stained with crystal violet. B, C, D) Three replicate
323 coupons were separately “treated” with sterile buffered water then neutralized. To harvest
324 and disaggregate, the coupons were vortexed (30 +/- 5 seconds) and sonicated (45 kHz, 10%
325 power, Sweep setting, 30 +/- 5 seconds) twice then received a final vortex. Images courtesy of
326 Danielle Orr and Blaine Fritz.

327

328 **Figure 2: Confocal microscopy images of coupons comparing two different sonication**
329 **settings.** Coupons (12.5X magnification) processed via sonication setting 1 (45 kHz, 10%
330 power, Sweep setting) on the left or sonication setting 2 (45 kHz, 100% power, Normal setting)
331 on the right.

332

333 **Figure 3. Confocal microscopy images of coupons comparing volumes, sonication liquid and**
334 **number of tubes.** Coupons (12.5X magnification) processed in 10 or 40 mL volumes, in dilution
335 water (DW) or D/E Neutralizing Broth (D/E), 3 or 12 tubes at a time with optimized sonication
336 setting (45 kHz, 100% power, Normal setting).

337

338 **Supplementary File 1: Key parameters of importance for harvesting and disaggregation.**

339

340 **DISCUSSION:**

341

342 **Minimum Information for Harvesting and Disaggregation Methods**

343 To create reproducible biofilm data across the scientific community, it is imperative that
344 authors include as much detail as possible regarding each of the growth, treatment, sampling
345 and analysis steps of a biofilm method. The standardization of biofilm methods has aided in
346 this endeavor as it allows the researcher to reference a specific method and any relevant
347 modifications. However, many papers include only a sentence or two to describe biofilm
348 harvesting and disaggregation. For better reproducibility, we recommend that minimum
349 information for biofilm harvesting be included in publications. This builds on the Minimum
350 Information About a Biofilm Experiment (MIABiE) initiative presented by Lourenco et al.¹⁷. In
351 the case of using sonication for biofilm harvesting and disaggregation parameters the
352 information should include: position of tubes within the bath (manufacturers’

353 recommendations to avoid damaging the transducers), number of tubes sonicated at the same
354 time, tube material, volume and type of liquid in the tube, presence of surfactant, position of
355 liquid in tubes relative to liquid level of ultrasonic bath, device used to hold the tubes in the
356 bath (glass beakers vs. test tube rack), degassing of water bath prior to sonication of samples
357 (if degassing is not a manufacturer option, simple operation of the bath before inserting the
358 samples will help remove some dissolved gasses from the bath liquid), temperature of water
359 bath (temperatures can rise after long periods of sonication), frequency (25 kHz or 45 kHz, for
360 example), bath function (sweep or normal, for example) and power range delivered to
361 transducers (10–100%, for example). These settings should be optimized for the biofilm being
362 studied, the system used to grow the biofilm and the specific make/model of ultrasonic bath¹⁸.

363

364 Sonicator settings may be changed to optimize desired harvesting effects. Degassing removes
365 dissolved air within the bath liquid thereby enhancing cleaning power. Frequency can be
366 adjusted to a low or high setting. A low setting such as 25 kHz, for example, would aid in
367 harvesting tenacious samples while a higher setting of 45 kHz would be more appropriate for
368 sensitive samples. A bath function of sweep or normal allows for distribution of cavitation.
369 The sweep function creates a continuous shifting of the sound pressure maxima. The normal
370 function allows the transducers to operate in double half wave mode which may result in dead
371 zones, thereby making the sonication less efficacious. Power ranges can be altered from 10 –
372 100% of the power delivered to the transducers¹⁹. It is known that sonication can
373 detrimentally effect bacterial viability. A 2008 study by Stamper et al.²⁰ exposed bacterial
374 cultures to increasing ultrasonic energy over time to create bacterial kill curves. We
375 recommend that users confirm that a particular combination of sonication settings does not
376 cause a decrease in viable bacteria²⁰.

377

378 There is no one perfect method to harvest and disaggregate biofilm, but particular methods
379 do work better for some surfaces/microbe combinations than others. We advocate for the
380 reader to determine which parameters are important for their particular biofilm scenario.
381 Key parameters of importance for harvesting and disaggregation are included in

382 **Supplementary File 1.**

383

384 For the sonication studies done to assess harvesting and disaggregation bias, we found that
385 sonication is convenient, efficient and able to be standardized for harvesting and
386 disaggregating biofilm from surfaces. Placement of coupons in vials minimizes technician to
387 technician variability that would be encountered in methods where coupons are physically
388 scraped by laboratory personnel, for example. Although it seems simple enough to place vials
389 in a sonicating water bath, there are many parameters that need to be considered to achieve
390 optimal harvesting of biofilm.

391

392 Two types of sonication equipment are available, ultrasonic baths and ultrasonic probes. This
393 paper focuses primarily on ultrasonic baths where ultrasonic energy is generated in the range
394 of high (20 – 45 kHz) to normal (40 – 60 Hz) frequency.

395

396 Three main processes are at play when using an ultrasonic device to clean a surface. Electrical

397 energy is converted to acoustic energy when a high frequency current is sent to a piezoelectric
398 or magnetostrictive transducer that oscillates in response to the current. The oscillation
399 generates compression (rarefaction) waves in the liquid. Cavitation bubbles form due to
400 negative pressure during rarefaction. The bubbles grow until they reach an unstable size and
401 collapse, creating a water jet that cleans surfaces²¹.

402

403 Three harvesting and disaggregation approaches are demonstrated in this article: sonication
404 and vortexing methods for harvesting and disaggregating biofilm when grown on
405 polycarbonate coupons in the CDC Biofilm Reactor according to the Single Tube Method.
406 Scraping and homogenization methods for harvesting and disaggregating biofilm are shown
407 when grown on glass coupons using the Drip Flow Biofilm Reactor. Scraping, sonication and
408 vortexing methods for harvesting and disaggregating biofilm are shown when grown in silicone
409 tubing.

410

411 There is no perfect method to harvest and disaggregate the biofilm, but some approaches are
412 better for different surfaces and/or applications. What is important is to take the time to
413 validate the method used. In this paper, we discussed the use of crystal violet and microscopy,
414 but other choices exist depending on the sensitivity required. If research includes efficacy
415 testing, then it is critical to confirm the validity of the approach in the presence of the
416 antimicrobial⁶. All equipment is slightly different, so even if the harvesting and disaggregation
417 method have been standardized, it is still prudent to confirm the process for the equipment
418 used. Harvesting and disaggregation methods are specific for surface associated and biofilm
419 bacteria. Research has demonstrated that improper choices may lead to biased test results.
420 Nonetheless, harvesting and disaggregation are the least studied of the four steps in biofilm
421 methods. It is generally also the unvalidated step (taken for granted as working) with the least
422 information present in published paper making it challenging to reproduce the process in a
423 different lab. This paper and accompanying video show three common approaches for two
424 surface types and suggests how to validate a method for an individual lab. This information
425 will help researchers make more informed decisions on which method to use and provides
426 guidance on what to report to improve reproducibility.

427

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433 The authors have no disclosures.

434

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